

RSE careers in France: the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) option

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In this talk, I will introduce the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS). The CNRS is an interdisciplinary public research organisation under the administrative supervision of the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research. Its main role is to advance knowledge for the benefit of society. It is the only French organisation for multidisciplinary research and a key player in international research, as well as a recognised innovator. It is a unique provider of researchers for universities but more importantly it offers a sustainable career path for engineers and technicians. The engineers and technicians from the CNRS contribute to and support research over 200 occupations from numerous professional fields, including sciences of the living world, chemical sciences, the humanities and social sciences, computer science, information, administration, and management. In this talk, I will focus in particular on the career of Research Software Engineer (RSE) via the CNRS and how RSEs contribute to the excellence of the French research in High Performance Computing.